

Development of the Accountability Dashboard in Ghana

Key Findings from an EdTech Hub sandbox

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Abbreviations and acronyms

API	Application Processing Interface
EMIS	Education Management Information System
GALOP	Ghana Accountability Learning Outcomes Project
GES	Ghana Education Service
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
MoE	Ministry of Education
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
mSRC	Mobile School Report Card
PBC	Project-Based Condition
PMDV	Performance Management and Data Visualisation Dashboard
SEND	Special Educational Needs and Disabilities

1. The story so far: The Accountability Dashboard

Development of Ghana's Ministry of Education (MoE) Accountability Dashboard is situated within EdTech Hub's broader, integrated support strategy to strengthen data use for decision-making across the education sector. The dashboard and its associated sandbox environment form one component of a coordinated approach that combines technical assistance, applied research, and system-level coordination.

This integrated model enables the Hub not only to support the development and refinement of digital tools but also to align them with policy priorities, build institutional capacity, and foster stakeholder collaboration. Within this ecosystem, the sandbox serves as a practical mechanism for iterative testing and user engagement, ensuring that the MoE Accountability dashboard is responsive to user needs and embedded within government processes.

The Accountability Dashboard, formerly known as the Performance Management and Data Visualisation Dashboard (PMDV), began as a response to a simple but persistent problem: education data existed across multiple agencies, but it was not easily accessible, comparable, or consistently used for decision-making. While MoE systems such as its Education Management Information System (EMIS) and the Mobile School Report Card (mSRC) generated valuable data, fragmentation limited their impact.

In 2019, the Ghana Accountability Learning Outcomes Project (GALOP) Accountability Framework ([World Bank, 2019](#)) provided the foundation for conceptualising a unified dashboard. The ambition was bold: to create a 'single source of truth' that would make priority education data accessible to managers across national, regional, district, and school levels.

Development formally commenced in 2020, with additional funding from the non-profit corporation BigWin Philanthropy, OeSD, the Austrian State Printing House, was contracted to build the platform. Over the next two years, GALOP funding supported the integration of the EMIS and mSRC data streams, laying the groundwork for cross-agency visualisation. Recognising that technology alone would not guarantee success, the MoE established a Systems Support Team in 2021, composed of agency representatives to provide technical and institutional guidance. By 2022, the dashboard was handed over to the MoE, signalling government ownership.

The initiative was anchored under two key GALOP Project-Based Conditions (PBCs):

- PBC 3.1: Ensuring that the dashboard was functional
- PBC 3.2: Increasing the number of schools using dashboard data during cluster-level meetings.

This shifted the focus from simply building a platform to embedding it into operational practice.

Between 2023 and 2024, efforts intensified to promote utilisation. Data capture mechanisms for cluster-level meetings were developed, and over 3,500 District Directors, School Improvement and Support Officers, and head teachers were trained across GALOP schools to use the dashboard effectively. By 2024, real-time or near-real-time data visualisation was enabled through APIs,¹ strengthening interoperability across agencies. That same year, an FCDO Accountable Grant was awarded to EdTech Hub to support the MoE in enhancing functionality and improving use.

The Accountable Grant was a year-long initiative intended to support the MoE's capacity to use data for planning, transparency, and accountability across the education system. It took an integrated approach that combined technical upgrades to the dashboard and data systems, such as the data glossary for common indicators.

The Grant also included complementary activities such as the systems mapping and the establishment of a steering committee.

Recognising the need for deeper institutional reform, 2025 marked a new phase: the MoE Accountability Dashboard would not only serve as a technological product but as part of a broader data governance and accountability reform, designed to move the MoE from fragmented data systems toward coordinated, evidence-informed decision-making across the education sector.

The dashboard was designed to pull data from multiple sources via an API. An integration layer 'translates' the data into a standardised format, allowing different data categories to be pulled into one consistent representation in the dashboard.

¹ An API (application programming interface) allows different systems to exchange information, securely and automatically.

Table 1. Illustrative examples of data types shared via the API to the PMDV Dashboard

Source	Dataset Examples
EMIS	Completion rate; gross enrolment ratio; net enrolment ratio; number of schools; population of learners
mSRC	Amount of grants received; number of teachers; number of trained teachers
National Council for Curriculum Assessment (NaCCA)	Learners proficient in English; numbers proficient in maths; number of schools participating in National Standardised Test (NST)
National School Inspectorate Authority (NaSIA)	Number of school inspections conducted; quality of overall school performance
National Teaching Council (NTC)	Number of licensed teachers in Ghana; teachers with at least one completed continuous professional development training

1.1. Challenges identified with the Accountability Dashboard

Despite this progress and investment, the Accountability Dashboard has faced persistent challenges. These are articulated in detail in the Situational Analysis of Data Governance Practices of Ministries of Education in Sub-Saharan Africa ([↑Korboe et al., Forthcoming](#)); as well as a Systems Mapping Study carried out prior to this Sandbox in 2025 ([↑Ampofo et al., Forthcoming a](#)). Key challenges are summarised below:

- Inconsistent indicator definitions:** Inconsistencies in data definition and interpretation. For example, there were discrepancies in how data held by the GES and in the EMIS was logged, for example, regarding what counted as a 'school'. The GES counted all facilities sharing a headteacher as one school, while in the EMIS these were logged separately.

- **Inconsistent collaboration and engagement:** Collaboration between agencies to align data policies remained ad hoc.
- **Lack of an operating system for the Accountability Dashboard:** Although there had been a handover from OeSD to MoE in 2022, there was no identifiable individual with the responsibility of ongoing management of the Accountability Dashboard, no identifiable user guides or technical documentation connected to the Dashboard. Additionally, the MoE and the Statistics, Research and Information Directorate (SRIM) did not have sufficient capacity to maintain the Accountability Dashboard on an ongoing basis, including responding to user feedback.
- **API issues:** Reviews also found that API calls frequently failed to load data into the dashboard. Some data (for example, from the EMIS) was being loaded through manual data dumps.
- **Infrastructure constraints:** Agencies reported ageing laptops, unreliable energy and weak internet connectivity as hindering their ability to collect and share data, and to access and analyse data from the Accountability dashboard.
- **User interface issues:** Some of the basic functionality of the Accountability Dashboard was found to be broken. For example, buttons frequently did not work, and fields/lists were found to be empty.
- **Lack of useful data:** Although many challenges focused on data quality and access, users generally felt the data did not meet their needs.

Building on the foundations laid by the existing dashboard, EdTech Hub, in partnership with the MoE, set out to design and test approaches to explore these challenges through the sandbox offer. See the introduction to this section for a brief overview of other activities undertaken by EdTech Hub in partnership with the MoE. For more detailed information, please see [Ampofo et al. \(Forthcoming b\)](#).

Our objective was to support the MoE to achieve its goal: data that improves decision-making and accountability.

1.2. The sandbox methodology

EdTech Hub sandboxes provide a team, toolkit, and approach to test and iterate on ideas in conditions of uncertainty. They combine innovation and research approaches to generate rapid, rigorous evidence, and then act on it. More information about the sandbox methodology and EdTech Hub's

open-source toolkit can be found in [↑Sandbox Handbook V.2.0 \(EdTech Hub, 2022\)](#).

Sandboxes begin with an overarching hypothesis about how an EdTech idea can lead to improvements in teaching and learning. Our hypothesis for this sandbox is shared in the image below:

If we...	brought together and visualised all education-related data in a 'single source of truth', where data was uniform (all data fields defined in the same way), accurate and consistent (without gaps),
Then...	government officials at all levels of the education system, and donor officials would use the data to inform decisions and highlight areas to focus/deepen their engagement,
So that...	education planning improves education outcomes.

After articulating a hypothesis, the sandbox team works in cycles of implementation and learning. In this sandbox, the team conducted three cycles over an eight-month period from June 2025 to January 2026.

Each cycle consisted of activities that aimed to generate evidence over a short period of time. These activities combined user research approaches, with developing prototypes and minimum viable products (MVPs), more common in innovation and lean impact.

[Figure 1](#) below illustrates the sandbox process.

Figure 1. *The sandbox process*

The process was adaptive: each cycle began and ended with a review, and the design of subsequent cycles depended on evidence from the preceding one. A summary of each cycle is shown in the [Table 2](#) below, followed by details on the user groups.

Over Cycles 1 to 3, the sandbox environment gradually moved from understanding user behaviour, to controlled prototype testing, to real-world MVP deployment and observation. In line with the iterative process outlined above, the prototype and MVP developed in Cycles 2 and 3 were informed by evidence from the preceding cycle.

A summary table of each cycle is provided below. Further details on the user groups are shared after [Table 2](#).

Table 2. *Summary of Sandbox cycles and user groups*

Cycle	Goal	Activities undertaken	User group(s)
Cycle 1	To understand user behaviours, barriers, and preferences to inform improvements to the MoE Accountability Dashboard that increase data use and data quality.	<p>User interviews, focus group discussions (FGDs) and observations</p> <p>60–90 minute interviews/FGDs with government officials selected from 2 districts across the education system and national donors, including a 30-minute observation of usage of the existing PMDV dashboard.</p>	All users participated in an interview or FGD and observation
Cycle 2	To validate a dashboard prototype through real-world engagement and user response.	<p>Prototype development and survey</p> <p>Based on insights from Cycle 1, EdTech Hub led the development of two dashboard prototypes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A prototype dashboard with two key indicators (attendance and National Standardised Test assessment scores), and customisable views by role. This was circulated broadly among all stakeholders. 2. A chatbot (built using ChatGPT’s custom GPT feature) allowing users to request and ‘chat’ about artificially generated data. This was shared with senior government officials and development partners 	<p>The prototype dashboard was sent to all users and additional Regional and District Education Directorates to enable a quantitative dataset. In total, 103 responses were collected.</p> <p>The AI-powered chatbot was sent only to national government officials and development partners. In total, 9 responses were collected.</p>

Cycle	Goal	Activities undertaken	User group(s)
Cycle 3	To gather rapid user feedback on our MVP, to inform ongoing development	MVP development and observation Development of a new iteration of the MoE Accountability Dashboard began in Cycle 3. Software development work prioritised implementing features highlighted in Cycles 1 and 2, including interface development for different user groups and a data export function. An MVP was shared with users, A 15-minute observation was carried out, followed by a 30-minute interview.	A subset of 36 representatives from schools, District Education Directorates, and donor officials participated in the observations.

1.3. User groups in the sandbox

As outlined in the sandbox hypothesis in [Section 1.2](#), the MoE Accountability Dashboard was intended to support users at all levels in the education system.

We worked closely with a cross-section of government officials at national, regional, district, and school levels from two districts representing rural and urban areas of the Greater Accra Region. This formed our core user group across all three cycles. In Cycle 2, we expanded our engagement to include Regional and District-level Education Directorates from across the country in our user group to generate reliable quantitative data (see below).

National government officials and donors

The dashboard is used by a range of national-level agencies within Ghana's Ministry of Education. Our sandbox user group included one official from:

- Directorate for Planning, Budgets, Monitoring & Evaluation (PBME)
- Directorate of Statistics, Research & Information Management (SRIM)
- Ghana Education Service (GES)
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NaCCA)
- National Schools Inspectorate Authority Responsible (NaSIA)
- National Teaching Council (NTC)

Additionally, the user group included a World Bank official, specifically, the official in charge of monitoring key indicators in the World Bank-funded Ghana Accountability for Learning Outcomes Project (GALOP) programme.

Other donors included in the user group:

- UK Foreign, Commonwealth & Development Office (FCDO)
- UNICEF

Regional Education Directorates

Two Regional Education Directorates were identified for the sandbox. One was located in Ga Central, an urban district close to Accra, and the other, Ada East, a rural district. Within these Directorates, all officials who used the PMDV dashboard were included in the user group, including:

- Regional Director

- EMIS Director
- Planning Director
- ICT and/or Statistics Manager

District Education Directorates

Four District Education Directorates were identified for the sandbox; two in each region. As with the Regional Education Directorates, all officials who used the PMDV dashboard were included in the user group. This included:

- District Director
- Head of Supervision
- Planning Officer
- ICT Officer
- Head of Statistics
- School Improvement and Support Officers (SISOs)

Schools

Four schools were identified for the sandbox: two primary and two secondary schools. Within these schools, the head teacher, deputy head teacher, and ICT teacher were included based on who engaged with the PMDV Dashboard in each school.

2. Key findings from the sandbox

Findings from the sandbox demonstrate strong demand for a more functional and user-centred MoE Accountability Dashboard, with 86% of surveyed officials indicating they would use the prototype weekly and 63% reporting it would influence their decision-making.

Users highlighted clear applications for data-driven decisions, including teacher allocation, performance management, and resource mobilisation, reinforcing the dashboard's potential to shift behaviours.

Enhancements such as disaggregated indicators significantly improved utilisation and perceived value.

However, challenges around timeliness and infrastructure remain key bottlenecks.

Overall, the findings validate the need for continued investment in integrated system improvements, data governance, interoperability and user-centred design to realise the full potential of data-driven decision making at the Ministry of Education.

2.1. The hypothesis holds

Officials at all levels of Ghana's public education system want to use the MoE Accountability Dashboard regularly and believe it will inform decision-making.

When presented with the prototype dashboard (developed based on user interviews and observations) in Cycle 2 of the sandbox, 86% said they would use it weekly or more regularly (of 95 responses across all levels of the education system). Of officers involved in statistics and planning, 43% said that, based on the prototype, they would use the dashboard on a daily basis.

Additionally, 63% (of 103 responses) of users selected '5' (very likely) or '6' (extremely likely) when asked "How likely will this dashboard change how you make decisions?"

Alongside this quantitative data, participants provided a clear overview of specific decisions and use cases that would be informed by the dashboard data. These included the use of data to:

- Engage caregivers and communities (especially by head teachers and District Education Directorates)

- Allocate teachers, including reclassification and reassignment (especially by Regional and District level officials)
- Manage performance, so different levels of the education systems can hold each other accountable for outcomes
- Request funding and other resources

Minding the intention-behaviour gap

Stated intentions are not the same as actual behaviour ([↑Koole et al., 2023](#)). These findings must be interpreted with caution. In particular, people tend to overestimate how much time or motivation they will have in the future. In spite of this, we believe this evidence is a strong signal of future usage and corresponding shifts in behaviour. This is further reinforced by the fact that, when the dashboard was shared with 800 people in WhatsApp groups representing District Education Directorates, 103 people (12.8%) explored the dashboard and completed the survey.

Evidence from other contexts

The sandbox findings reflect emerging evidence on the positive impact of data dashboards on decision-making, from other contexts. In Kenya, as part of the Tusome programme, over 1,200 curriculum support officers were equipped with tablets that collected classroom observation and student assessment data, feeding into a national dashboard visible to MoE officials at every level. This shifted behaviour. For example, when the dashboard revealed that a 2018 curriculum change that cut reading lessons from five to three per week was eroding literacy gains, MoE officials used that evidence to reverse the decision, restoring lesson time ([↑Piper et al., 2017; 2018](#)). In South Africa, data-driven districts — providing dashboards with data on attendance and performance — have also shown promising signals of impact ([↑Stasiewski, 2024](#)).

The above-cited examples validate our hypothesis that users would engage with a dashboard that was uniform, accurate, and consistent, and it could shift their decision-making behaviour.

Low awareness of the existing dashboard

One barrier to usage was low awareness of the existing MoE Accountability Dashboard. In Cycle 1 interviews, a majority of interviewees at Regional and District Education Directorates and schools were using the dashboard for the first time.

Relatedly, ‘lack of ownership of the dashboard’ was the most repeated theme in Cycle 1 interviews (7 occurrences), echoing a lack of familiarity and use within routine practice, especially at the sub-national level.

2.2. More granularity, more customisation, more utility

Users’ willingness to engage with the dashboard was linked to the granularity of relevant detail available.

Users at all levels of the education system expressed a strong preference for detailed, customised, role-relevant data. This came through strongly in the thematic analysis of Cycle 1 interviews. Recurring themes included ‘the need for more granular indicators’ (6 occurrences) and ‘the need for different data’ (5 occurrences).

All themes that occurred three or more times are listed in [Table 3](#) below.

Table 3. Summary of higher-order themes from Cycle 1 interviews and observations

Theme	Number of occurrences
Lack of ownership of dashboard (especially at school level)	7
Constraints among data generators	6
Need for more granular indicators	6
Tech and connectivity challenges	6
The need for different data	5
Lack of trust in the data	5
The data is not reliable	5
Lack of integration of data sources	4
School codes not unified	3
Need for automation in data collection	3

Prototype development in Cycle 2 focused on addressing the needs highlighted in bold in [Table 3 above](#). The prototype dashboard:

- Featured ‘role-based views’ (see [Figure 2](#) below). Users could select whether they represented the national education system, or a specific region, district, or school, and receive a customised set of data.
- Visualised key indicators, showing how they changed over time, and provided benchmarks against the national average, and the average for

that region or district. This enabled users to ‘drill down’ to specific indicators.

We believe that this set of features played a significant role in the positive user feedback of the prototype dashboard. In addition, users who provided comments in their feedback form shared that the prototype dashboard was ‘easier to navigate’, ‘easy to assess and simple, making it easy to use’, and it would allow them to ‘track progress’, thereby validating that addressing this need for granularity and customisation will increase usability and utility.

Figure 2. Screen shot of prototype dashboard, depicting role-based views

Figure 3. Screenshot of prototype dashboard, depicting data and comparison to the national average

From interesting data to actionable data

When expressing the need for more granular and different indicators, users expressed that the current dashboard focused on indicators in the [Education Strategic Plan 2018–2030 \(Ministry of Education, 2019\)](#), and the [Ghana Accountability for Learning Outcomes Project \(World Bank, 2025\)](#).

At all levels, users found this data interesting but not specific enough to inform or take action. Data on national test scores or attendance must be disaggregated by school, district, and region. Additionally, more granular indicators, breaking down data by gender, age group, etc., would enable more targeted action.

Informing the roadmap for future development

As part of the Accountable Grant deliverables, a comprehensive roadmap was co-developed with the MoE to guide the phased strengthening of data systems, governance, and use for decision-making.

Adding more granular and customised data from across various agencies in Ghana's MoE is a top priority for the ongoing development of the dashboard. This includes ongoing scaling and iteration of the features outlined above. In addition, a long-term goal is to articulate, within the dashboard, potential causal relationships between different indicators, so users can take more informed action to improve specific indicators.

The inclusion of indicators for special educational needs and disabilities (SEND), as requested by the Special Education Directorate, was identified as a critical step. Ensuring that data on learners with SEND is represented would make the dashboard more inclusive and equitable. Additionally, adding data from additional agency datasets such as the Ghana Statistical Service and the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection, was also identified as important.

As a first step, EdTech Hub conducted a mapping exercise of all available indicators across different agencies, creating a list of possible indicators to be visualised and upon further agency engagement, selected priority indicators that were integrated into the dashboard. Understanding and alignment on data available at the national level is a necessary precondition to visualising granular, customisable data.

2.3. Data input is a significant bottleneck.

The ability to build a useful dashboard is constrained by limitations in the data feeding into it

While demand for the dashboard is strong, users highlighted 'constraints among data generators' (6 occurrences), 'tech and connectivity challenges' (6 occurrences), 'lack of trust in the data' (5 occurrences), and 'the data is not reliable' in Cycle 1 interviews.

These responses reflect findings about inconsistent data quality identified in studies carried out prior to the sandbox (see [Section 1.2](#) above). Specifically, the sandbox identified:

- **Lack of real-time data:** A significant part of the perception of the data not being reliable was that the data was not 'real-time data'. Current, up-to-date data was a large driver for usage and utility. Interviews and observations in Cycles 1 and 3 confirmed that the existing dashboard relies on periodic manual data dumps rather than live API calls, which take place irregularly. In the words of one stakeholder, "Delays in submission will result in loss of interest from stakeholders."
- **Flawed and missing data:** Manual data uploads, combined with failed API calls, lead to gaps and inaccuracies that undermine trust in the data.
- **Tech and connectivity challenges:** Agencies reported ageing laptops, unreliable energy supply and weak internet connectivity as limiting their ability to collect, submit, and access data.
- **School codes:** The absence of standardised school identifiers across agencies is a significant barrier to data harmonisation. Different agencies use different school codes, meaning data from different sources cannot be reliably matched to the same school.

Addressing this challenge at the level of data output

Data input challenges are not solely technical: they also reflect political and institutional dynamics. The sandbox focused on the data 'output', and therefore these challenges were largely out of scope.

EdTech Hub has worked with MoE to address these challenges through targeted capacity building and institutional ownership.

However, one feature introduced in the prototype dashboard improved accountability for data input. Data now includes a 'last updated' tag, showing

when it was updated with a red/amber/green light indicating recency. This feature was supported with positive feedback and will be maintained in future iterations of the dashboard.

2.4. The complementary chatbot

A chat-based interface holds potential as a supplement, for now.

In Cycle 2, the sandbox tested a chat-based interface built using ChatGPT's custom GPT feature alongside the data visualisation prototype. The chatbot was designed to allow users to request and converse about artificially generated data and was shared only with national government officials and donors to manage expectations around AI development.

Figure 4. Screenshot of prototype chatbot

Compared to the data visualisation prototype, the chatbot had lower usage intent and lower stated influence on decision-making; 55% of users selected a score of 5+ (out of 6) on a Likert scale relating to the question 'How likely will this dashboard change how you make decisions?' (63% for data visualisation), and 55% claimed they would use it weekly or more (86% for data visualisation).

While the sample of 9 participants is too small to draw overall conclusions, an emerging insight from the qualitative survey feedback is that more complex, conversational use cases currently exist only for a subset of users; the majority appear to want a 'reference' tool rather than a chat interface.

Therefore, a chat-based interface, integrated into (rather than separate from) the data visualisation, holds promise as a complement. The cost and data privacy implications would need to be considered during further implementation.

3. Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the findings above, we outline six key recommendations. If you are building or implementing a dashboard visualising education data to inform decision-making, read on to understand how our insights might apply to your work.

- **Start with data governance and ownership:** Technical challenges encountered in this sandbox, such as unreliable and missing data, API call failures, and misaligned school codes, were symptoms of a deeper challenge: a lack of ownership and responsibility for accurate, consistent and uniform data. Therefore, any work on data visualisation and dashboards must be accompanied by behavioural work to make sure the right people are aligned, motivated, and clear on their responsibilities for collecting, maintaining, and inputting data.
- **Map and bring all stakeholders into the process:** Linked to the above bullet point, all key stakeholders must be involved from the outset, so all agencies and levels of the education system that input and access data are invested in a dashboard's success. In Ghana, this included all MoE agencies, regional, district, and school-level officials, as well as donors, including the UK Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO), World Bank, and Big Win Philanthropy.
- **Connect software engineering with education system leadership:** Developing a dashboard requires clear ownership, from a software engineer (or engineering team) and MoE leadership. Technical issues must be 'owned' and resolved quickly to maintain trust in a dashboard. At the same time, many issues are non-technical. These include the capacity of teams (particularly at the school, district, and regional levels) to submit data, political will to input data, and alignment on key indicators and definitions. These require relationship management, communication, and institutional knowledge.
- **Avoid data without a clear 'so what':** Every indicator you include in a dashboard should pass a simple test of being able to answer the question: What can the person looking at this actually do with it? Users wanted granular and relevant data to inform the actual decisions they needed to make. This deceptively simple question should guide product decisions.
- **Be strict with prioritisation:** Throughout the sandbox, officials at all levels of the education system provided detailed and thoughtful

feedback on what the dashboard should include. Officials at different levels of the education system and within different agencies had different needs. Without a disciplined approach to prioritising product features and data indicators, we risked our product roadmap becoming unmanageable and the dashboard becoming too bloated.

During development of the prototype in Cycle 2, as well as the MVP in Cycle 3, we applied the MoSCoW framework (categorising requests as 'must have', 'should have', 'could have' and 'won't have [for now]'). This allowed us to assess trade-offs and prioritise a dashboard that met a majority of needs without overwhelming the user.

- **Ship early and keep testing and iterating:** In this sandbox, we gathered significant evidence by sharing two prototypes, built in days at minimal cost. By providing a prototype that users could engage with, we surfaced insights beyond those from interviews and observations with the existing PMDV dashboard. Sentiment and clickthrough data provided a signal we could act on, and served as a proxy (alongside qualitative insights) for evidence on sustained usage and behaviour change.

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<https://docs.edtechhub.org/lib/JWVN28UJ>

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